

Bridging Clusters: A Comparative Look at Multi-Cluster Networking Performance in Kubernetes

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Abstract

Microservices and containers have transformed the way applications are developed, tested, deployed, scaled, and managed. Several container orchestration platforms, like Kubernetes, have emerged, streamlining container management at scale and providing enterprise-grade support for application modernization. Driven by application, compliance, and end-user requirements, companies opt to deploy multiple Kubernetes clusters across public and private clouds. However, deploying applications in multi-cluster environments presents distinct challenges, especially managing the communication between the microservices spread across clusters. Traditionally, custom configurations, like VPNs or firewall rules, were required to connect such complex setups of clusters spanning the public cloud and on-premise infrastructure. This industry paper presents a comprehensive analysis of network performance characteristics for three popular open-source multi-cluster networking solutions (namely, Skupper, Submariner, and Istio), addressing the challenges of microservices connectivity across clusters. We evaluate key factors such as latency, throughput, and resource utilization using established tools and benchmarks, offering valuable insights for organizations aiming to optimize the network performance of their multi-cluster deployments. Our experiments revealed that each solution involves unique trade-offs in performance and resource efficiency: Submariner offers low latency and consistency, Istio excels in throughput with moderate resource consumption, and Skupper stands out for its ease of configuration while maintaining balanced performance.

CCS Concepts

• **General and reference** → **Measurement**; • **Networks** → **Network performance evaluation**; • **Computer systems organization** → **Distributed architectures**.

Keywords

Kubernetes, Multi-Cluster Networking, Network Performance, Distributed Microservices, Benchmark

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1 Introduction

The shift towards microservices has revolutionized modern application design and deployment, allowing for scalable, modular, and resilient architectures. Containers enhance this by offering lightweight, portable environments to run these services. However, containers alone do not provide the management features required for tasks like scaling, fault tolerance, and networking. To bridge this gap, orchestration tools like Kubernetes have become crucial, automating the management of containerized microservices [18]. According to the Cloud Native Computing Foundation's most recent annual survey [20], 84% of end-user organizations (excluding cloud vendors) are using Kubernetes in production or evaluating it. The presence of an active upstream community, a roadmap that is agile enough to meet the evolving demands of enterprises, platform agnostic design, extensibility, modularity, and strong vendor support have all positioned Kubernetes as the leading container orchestration framework.

Kubernetes provides a versatile platform for managing applications, offering configurations for single-cluster and multi-cluster deployments. A single cluster can effectively serve a wide range of needs, accommodating everything from small development environments to large, multi-tenant architectures. As application and compliance requirements grow more complex, organizations often find a multi-cluster Kubernetes environment necessary. Multi-cluster Kubernetes refers to using multiple clusters, which may be hosted across different physical locations or cloud environments, coordinated through appropriate management tools and processes.

While single-cluster deployments provide simplified management, reduced operational overhead, and cost efficiency, as all resources are consolidated in one environment [17], multi-cluster deployments provide several advantages [24, 34]: They allow for tenant isolation, creating distinct environments for development,

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staging, and production, which can be difficult to manage within a single cluster. Additionally, multi-cluster deployments improve availability and performance by facilitating workload migration between clusters. Additional benefits include enhanced failover capabilities, compliance with geographic and regulatory requirements, and greater scalability through application distribution and bursting across clusters. Moreover, multi-cluster environments are particularly valuable for edge computing and distributed systems, where localized processing is crucial.

Despite the numerous advantages, managing a multi-cluster environment presents significant complexity. A key challenge is facilitating communication among microservices distributed across different clusters. For example, connecting clusters spanning public cloud and on-premise infrastructure has traditionally required custom configurations like VPNs or firewall rules. According to the Cloud Native Computing Foundation’s Tech Radar report [19], no single multi-cluster management solution dominates the landscape. Instead, organizations have adopted various approaches, with equal prevalence of custom in-house tools, private cloud-managed Kubernetes, and public cloud-managed Kubernetes solutions. In this industry paper, we evaluate three state-of-the-art multi-cluster networking solutions (namely, Skupper [12], Submariner [13], and Istio [3]), providing insights into their performance to guide the selection of appropriate tools for their specific needs.

Our evaluation reveals distinct performance and resource efficiency trade-offs, with each solution excelling in specific scenarios. For instance, Submariner offers low latency and resource efficiency, which are ideal for applications requiring consistent performance, while Istio provides higher throughput with moderate resource consumption, albeit with some variability in latency.

The remainder of this industry paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces multi-cluster Kubernetes and reviews related work. Section 3 outlines the measurement setup, deployed multi-cluster networking solutions, and performed test cases. Section 4 compares the results of the multi-cluster networking solutions. Section 5 summarizes the paper. Section 6 discusses future work.

2 Background

In this section, we first introduce containerization and Kubernetes. Next, we explore the differences between Kubernetes’ single-cluster and multi-cluster deployments. We then provide an overview of multi-cluster networking. Finally, we discuss related work and highlight how our research distinguishes itself from existing studies.

2.1 Containerization and Kubernetes

Containerization is a type of technology that enables the encapsulation of applications and their dependencies within lightweight, isolated units called containers that can be run across diverse environments on-premises and in the cloud. Unlike traditional virtual machines (VMs), which require dedicated operating system kernels and result in substantial resource overhead, containers share the host system’s kernel, reducing the footprint of individual workloads. Containers’ ability to create consistent environments across diverse infrastructures has been a key factor in the technology’s adoption in both development and production environments, facilitating reproducibility and portability. The container for the application has

all the libraries, dependencies, files, and configurations required to run it consistently across any environment, which greatly reduces the time spent dealing with environment-related side-effects and increases the speed of innovation. Microservices deployed as containers have become indispensable in today’s software engineering paradigms and have truly helped application modernization take off significantly. Technologies like Docker [22] and Podman [11] can help manage containers on a single machine but are not very well designed to handle multi-container and multi-host setups.

Kubernetes [5] is a container orchestration system designed to automate containerized applications’ deployment, scaling, and management in distributed environments. While containerization tools like Docker and Podman effectively address containerization at the node level, Kubernetes extends this functionality by orchestrating containers across a cluster of machines, making it possible to manage and scale thousands of containers in dynamic, large-scale environments. Deploying and managing Web-scale applications using microservices and containers can become an insurmountable problem without an orchestration system like Kubernetes, which abstracts the underlying infrastructure nuances away. The architecture of Kubernetes (see Figure 1) is based on several core concepts, including *Pods*, which represent the smallest deployable unit in Kubernetes, typically composed of one or more tightly coupled containers; *Nodes*, which are the worker machines (physical or virtual) where containers are deployed; and the *Control plane*, which manages the cluster’s state, scheduling, and orchestration. Kubernetes has become the de facto standard for container orchestration in cloud-native environments and, in the process, has helped an entire ecosystem of ancillary technologies thrive with it.

2.2 Single-Cluster vs. Multi-Cluster

Kubernetes can be deployed in two common configurations: single-cluster and multi-cluster, each offering unique advantages and use cases. In a single-cluster deployment, all workloads and resources are managed within one Kubernetes cluster, as illustrated in Figure 1. Since there is only one control plane, deployment, configuration, and monitoring are simplified. Applications within the cluster can share resources, often resulting in efficient use of compute and storage. Inter-service communication within the same cluster typically experiences lower latency, enhancing overall application performance. The unified environment also allows for consistent execution of operations like upgrades, scaling, and security policies. However, single-cluster deployments may encounter challenges with scalability and fault tolerance. As the number of applications increases, resource contention can degrade performance, and a single point of failure could impact the entire application ecosystem.

Compared to single-cluster deployments, multi-cluster Kubernetes deployments involve managing multiple clusters across different environments, regions, or cloud providers. This approach allows organizations to optimize clusters for specific workloads, enhancing scalability and resource management. Organizations can isolate faults by distributing workloads across clusters, ensuring issues in one cluster don’t impact others. Multi-cluster deployments can also improve performance for global applications by reducing latency, placing clusters closer to end users. Furthermore, clusters can be configured to meet specific security, data governance, and

Figure 1: Single-cluster deployment architecture overview.

Figure 2: Multi-cluster deployment architecture overview.

regulatory requirements (e.g., General Data Protection Regulation), providing greater control over data access and resource allocation. For example, the database of an application can be hosted on a secure private cluster, while the front-end can be hosted on a separate public-facing cluster. However, managing multi-cluster environments introduces complexity in orchestration and resource coordination, often increasing operational overhead. Additionally, inter-cluster communication may encounter higher latency than communication within a single cluster. 43% of all organizations surveyed [20] are using a hybrid cloud architecture (at least one private and one public cloud that are somewhat integrated), which underscores the growing importance of the multi-cluster paradigm in Kubernetes production deployments.

2.3 Multi-Cluster Networking

While having a multi-cluster Kubernetes deployment offers numerous benefits, it also presents specific challenges, particularly regarding communication between microservices or applications located in different clusters. Establishing connections between microservices deployed across multiple Kubernetes clusters, whether on-premises or with cloud providers, requires specialized configurations such as VPN or firewall rules. This networking challenge becomes even more significant when at least one of the clusters is private or situated behind a DMZ, limiting its ability to accept incoming network connections or lacking ingress routes. To tackle these challenges, several solutions have emerged to address the complexities of multi-cluster networking.

In this industry paper, we examine the performance of three open-source solutions: **Skupper** [12], **Submariner** [13], and **Istio** [3]. Each solution focuses on enabling seamless application connectivity and service discovery across clusters without code

modifications, VPN setups, or firewall configurations. However, they operate at different layers of the ISO/OSI stack and employ distinct approaches to solve the problem, which can result in performance variations. For example, Skupper operates at layer 7 by establishing a virtual application network, Submariner operates at layer 3 by creating tunnels between the clusters, and Istio implements a service mesh across the clusters. Each solution is introduced in more detail in Section 3.1.

2.4 Related Work

Existing research on multi-cluster networking for containers can be broadly categorized into two main areas: (i) performance evaluation of the network and (ii) development of methods to enhance networking efficiency. In the first category, Javadi et al. [23] investigated the performance of multi-cluster networks theoretically without presenting experimental results. In contrast, Atici and Boluk [1], Park et al. [32], and Suo et al. [33] conducted performance analyses but focused solely on single-cluster environments. Similarly, Liu and Guitart [26] compared network performance, though their study was limited to HPC workloads. Morabito et al. [30] also examined performance, but focusing on communication between two IoT frameworks. In the second category, Govindarajan et al. [21], Osmani et al. [31], Martin et al. [28], and Bruschi et al. [16] each propose network solutions aimed at improving efficiency between clusters. Meanwhile, Lee et al. [25], Tamiru et al. [34], and Mfula et al. [29] introduced mechanisms to optimize the scheduling and orchestration of containers within the network.

Our work investigates multi-cluster solutions using several key metrics, focusing on networks spanning multiple clusters rather than single-cluster environments. Unlike previous studies, which often limit their scope to theoretical analysis or a single cluster, our experiments are grounded in real-world, industry-driven contexts, providing practical insights into network performance and efficiency across diverse, large-scale deployments.

3 Measurement Setup

In this section, we begin by introducing the deployed multi-cluster networking solutions. Next, we describe the testbed utilized for our evaluation. Following that, we detail the traffic flow associated with the networking solutions. We then outline the process of workload generation. Afterward, we explain how we measured the overhead. Finally, we discuss the employed workload generation methods.

3.1 Multi-Cluster Networking Solutions

In this section, we present each deployed multi-cluster networking solution and highlight the performance differences among them. Table 1 provides a brief overview of each solution.

Skupper [12] is an open-source layer 7 service connectivity solution that enables secure communication between services across multiple Kubernetes clusters and Podman environments without the need for VPNs or firewall configurations. It creates a Virtual Application Network (VAN), by using layer 7 application routers. Once a Skupper network is formed across Kubernetes namespaces on different clusters, any service in those namespaces can be exposed on the VAN, allowing them to interact as though they are part of a single network. Skupper's key features include:

Table 1: Comparison of features and characteristics of the investigated multi-cluster networking solutions.

	Skupper	Submariner	Istio
Operation layer	L4	L3	L4/L7
Network topology	Point to point	Hub/spoke	Network mesh
Inter-connect level	Namespace	Cluster	Service
Service discovery	✓	✓	✓
Security features	mTLS	IPsec	mTLS
Authentication policies	Limited	✗	✓
Integrated observability	Limited	Limited	✓
Configuration Complexity	Low	Low	High
CNI independence	✓	✗	✓
Traffic management	✗	✗	✓
Multicloud support	✓	✓	✓
End user persona	Developer	Cluster admin	Cluster admin, Developer
License	Apache 2.0	Apache 2.0	Apache 2.0
CNCF hosted	✗	✓	✓

- No changes required to the application code
- Ability to setup the VAN without administrator privileges
- Support for HTTP/1.1, HTTP/2, gRPC, and TCP communication
- Application of mTLS for secure inter-cluster communication
- Redundant routing mechanisms to ensure high availability

Submariner [13] is a Kubernetes project providing a simple and scalable solution for interconnecting multiple Kubernetes clusters across different data centers or cloud providers. It enables applications running in one cluster to seamlessly communicate with those running in other clusters, making them behave like they are part of the same logical network. This is achieved by establishing secure tunnels between clusters, with the default implementation being IPsec with Libreswan [6]. Alternatives such as WireGuard [15] and un-encrypted tunnels using Virtual Extensible LAN (VXLAN) implementation are also available. These encrypted or unencrypted tunnels create a unified, cross-cluster network, enabling service discovery and communication across clusters while maintaining cluster isolation where necessary. Submariner’s key features include:

- Automatic discovery of other clusters on the same network
- Ability to create a network overlay between clusters for direct application communication without additional configurations
- Definition of policies to control traffic flow between clusters
- Support for multiple cloud providers, including Amazon Web Services, Microsoft Azure, and Google Cloud Platform

Istio [3] is an advanced service mesh that acts as an infrastructure layer, providing applications capabilities such as security, observability, and traffic management. While it is primarily used for intra-cluster communication, it can also cover multiple clusters in different cloud environments within a single mesh. Istio also offers capabilities like fault isolation and location-aware routing. For setting up the multi-cluster mesh on bare metal clusters, an additional component called MetalLB [7] needs to be installed and configured. Istio’s key features include:

- No changes required to the application code
- Comprehensive zero-trust security solution
- Generation of telemetry within the service mesh to provide useful performance metrics
- Definition of traffic routing rules to control flow
- Support for multiple deployments, including traditional side-car (used in this paper) and ambient mode.

3.2 Testbed Description

We performed all experiments on bare metal environments to avoid the influence of cloud variability. Two clusters were set up in a managed enterprise data center environment with Red Hat owned equipment, each consisting of five servers (three control plane and two worker nodes). Each enterprise server, Dell R640, runs *Red Hat OpenShift v4.16* (based on *Kubernetes v1.29*), which is an enterprise-grade Kubernetes distribution with Platform-as-a-Service capabilities, and features the following hardware configuration:

- CPU: 40 x Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6230 CPU @ 2.10GHz
- Memory: 376 GiB
- Disk: Solid state devices
- Network: Broadcom NetXtreme-E 25Gb RDMA

The Container Network Interface (CNI) plugin deployed on both clusters was Open Virtual Networking - Kubernetes (OVN-Kubernetes) [10], an open-source project that provides a robust networking solution for Kubernetes clusters with Open Virtual Networking (OVN) [9] and Open Virtual Switch (Open vSwitch) [35] at its core.

The components associated with the multi-cluster networking solution under test were isolated to a specific node (labeled gateway node) using Kubernetes *nodeAffinity* to prevent interference with workload performance and ensure accurate overhead measurement. The network performance measurement tools were run on the other worker, labeled as data-plane node, as shown in Figure 3.

To reduce variability and improve determinism of network performance, a *Performance Profile* was applied to the clusters, reserving specific cores for the operational system and housekeeping

Figure 3: Overview of the testbed setup. To prevent interference, the networking solution is deployed on a gateway node, while the performance measurement tools run on a data-plane node.

tasks and isolating the rest to host the workload. The pods running the networking tests were configured with isolated CPU cores allocated on the same NUMA node as the corresponding network interfaces. The client and server pods had CPU requests and limits equal to 4 whole CPU cores.

A container image based on *Red Hat Universal Base Image 9* was built to include the necessary network performance measurement and debugging tools. This container was run as a pod through a Kubernetes *Deployment* and configured either as a client or server, always placed on the data-plane node. When operating in the server mode, the deployment was exposed through a Kubernetes *Service* of type *ClusterIP*. All the necessary files and configuration for replicating the test setup on any environment can be found here [27].

Skupper v1.8.1, Submariner v0.18.9, and Istio Mesh v1.23.2 were deployed on both clusters. In the case of Submariner, the first Kubernetes cluster acts as the hub, and subsequently, the second one joined as a spoke cluster. Submariner and Istio frameworks follow the operator pattern. Operators are software extensions to Kubernetes that use Custom Resource Definitions (CRDs) and controllers to manage applications.

Each multi-cluster networking solution includes its own set of additional configurations and tuning options. However, we only considered the default, out-of-the-box configuration for our evaluation. We did so for two key reasons: to assess performance from the end-user’s perspective for broader industry relevance and to maintain fairness and simplicity in our comparisons.

To add another dimension to the comparative analysis, the **Kubernetes-based Efficient Power Level Exporter (Kepler)** [4] was deployed on the clusters as a Prometheus exporter. It uses eBPF to probe CPU performance counters and Linux kernel tracepoints. This data and stats from cgroup and sysfs can then be fed into ML models to estimate energy and power consumption at the container level. Kepler can also extract real-time power consumption metrics from the node components through API integrations like Redfish from the Baseboard Management Controller (BMC).

3.3 Traffic Flow Description

Skupper - Cluster interconnection works in Layer 7 (application layer) without the need to create any VPNs or special firewall rules. Skupper works according to the VAN approach, connecting applications and services in the cluster into a virtual network so that they can communicate with each other as if they were all running on the same site.

As it can be observed in Figure 4, Skupper creates a Kubernetes Service within the same namespace that forwards traffic to the corresponding Skupper router pod. The *Skupper Router* is responsible for load-balancing requests across pods as part of the Skupper network. In our testbed, the Skupper router pod was intentionally placed on a Gateway node to isolate its resource overhead impact from the workload.

Figure 4: Skupper traffic flow.

Submariner - Traffic leaves the client pod hosted in the worker node towards the gateway node through Submariner route agents running as a Kubernetes daemonset on all schedulable nodes of the cluster. These agents are responsible for routing cross-cluster traffic from the nodes to the active Gateway Engine. In the cluster’s gateway node(s), the Submariner Gateway Engine is responsible for managing the secure tunnels to other clusters and routing the traffic into the multi-cluster continuum. Finally, the Service Discovery component propagates the corresponding DNS entries when the services are exposed through the Submariner API.

In the destination cluster, we observe mirrored network traffic flow, with data arriving at the Gateway Engine and being cross-routed by the route agents to the destination server pod on the corresponding data-plane node, as depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Submariner traffic flow.

Istio - Multi-cluster deployment model consists of a mesh spread across different clusters. These clusters can be inter-connected in different ways through istio mesh. In our setup, the clusters were connected in a *multi-primary on different networks* configuration.

Istio supports two main data plane modes: (i) **Sidecar mode**, which deploys an Envoy proxy along with each pod that you start in the cluster; (ii) **Ambient mode**, which uses a per-node Layer 4 proxy, and optionally a per-namespace Envoy proxy for Layer 7 features.

Istio has been built on the sidecar pattern from its first release in 2017. Sidecar mode is well understood and thoroughly battle-tested,

but comes with a resource cost and operational overhead. Ambient mode was built to address the shortcomings reported by users of sidecar mode, but it is only production-ready for single-cluster use cases and thus was not considered for this paper.

As shown in Figure 6, traffic leaves the client pod after being processed and forwarded by the *envoy* sidecar container. It leaves cluster 1 using the node’s default gateway and reaches cluster 2 after first passing through the east-west gateway, which forwards the traffic to the server’s sidecar container, and this envoy proxy finally forwards it to the server application. Note that the client and server pods run on worker nodes in Cluster 1 and 2, respectively, and the gateway pod runs on a gateway node in Cluster 2.

Figure 6: Istio traffic flow.

3.4 Layer 4 Workload Generation

To evaluate the network performance on Layer 4 of the ISO/OSI stack for the multi-cluster networking solutions of interest, we utilize the **uperf** [14] micro-benchmark with different traffic profiles to simulate real-world traffic patterns. We chose uperf due to its flexibility and configurability, allowing us to model a wide range of traffic profiles with varying packet sizes. In our setup, uperf is configured with separate sender and receiver instances, each running in its own container. For the different test cases, we vary both the message sizes (ranging from 64B to 8KB) and the number of concurrent threads (1, 2, and 4) to saturate the link and apply sufficient load on the System under Test (SUT). The number of threads represents the number of concurrent “users” on the sending node, simulating different traffic intensities. Each performed experiments with uperf lasts for 1 minute and is repeated 5 times. Below, we introduce the test scenarios executed with uperf.

The **stream**/throughput profile performs a bulk data transfer where the client opens a connection and keeps writing data for the duration of the test before closing the connection, as shown in Listing 1. The key performance indicator (KPI) for these tests is throughput in Gbps.

```

1 <?xml version="1.0"?>
2 <profile name="throughput">
3   <group nthreads="$nthr">
4     <transaction iterations="1">
5       <flowop type="connect"
6         options="remotehost=$uperf_service_host
7         protocol=tcp
8         port=$uperf_service_port_uperf_data"/>
9     </transaction>
10    <transaction duration="60s">
11      <flowop type="write" options="size=$size"/>
12    </transaction>
13    <transaction iterations="1">
14      <flowop type="disconnect" />
15    </transaction>

```

```

16 </group>
17 </profile>

```

Listing 1: Throughput intensive profile.

Request-Response refers to a series of experiments we conducted to assess the number of transactions that can be processed in one second. For these tests, the client opens a connection, keeps it open, and then transfers data in the form of an equal sized writes and reads for the duration of the test before closing the connection, as shown in Listing 2. The KPI for these tests is the number of transactions per second.

```

1 <?xml version="1.0"?>
2 <profile name="rr">
3   <group nthreads="$nthr">
4     <transaction iterations="1">
5       <flowop type="connect" options="remotehost=$
6         uperf_service_host protocol=tcp port=$
7         uperf_service_port_uperf_data"/>
8     </transaction>
9     <transaction duration="60s">
10      <flowop type=write options="size=$size"/>
11      <flowop type=read options="size=$size"/>
12    </transaction>
13    <transaction iterations="1">
14      <flowop type="disconnect" />
15    </transaction>

```

Listing 2: Request-Response profile.

3.5 Layer 7 Workload Generation

We used **wrk2** [37] to assess the Layer 7 network performance of the multi-cluster networking solutions. wrk2 is an HTTP benchmarking tool mostly based on wrk [36]. We chose wrk2 because of its capability to operate at a constant rate of throughput for measuring the latency accurately. On the server side, **nginx** [8] was chosen as the HTTP web server. Both wrk2 client and the nginx server were deployed in separate pods, each in a different cluster. This benchmark was run using a message size of 1024B and at a constant throughput of 10,000 requests per second, using 2 threads and keeping 100 connections open. Each experiment was conducted five times, lasting one minute per run, focusing on latency in milliseconds as the KPI.

3.6 Resource Overhead Measurement

Resource consumption, and by extension, the overhead incurred, is a critical factor when evaluating multi-cluster networking solutions. Therefore, we isolated the pods of each multi-cluster networking solutions to a single worker node in each cluster labeled as *gateway* to measure the overhead accurately and consistently as much as possible. The remaining worker node in each cluster was earmarked for running the client/server pods that ran the test cases. The overhead added by the multi-cluster networking solution was calculated by measuring the CPU usage on the gateway node during the test runs and subtracting that from CPU usage observed on the gateway node in an idle cluster without the workload. By doing this on both clusters and adding the overhead observed in each cluster, the total overhead of the multi-cluster networking solution was obtained. Specifically for Istio mesh, where it was not entirely possible to

isolate the components onto a dedicated node due to the sidecar mode, the overhead on the gateway node was added to the CPU usage of each of the sidecar containers of the client and server pods to calculate the cumulative overhead. The KPI for these tests is the incurred CPU utilization overhead.

3.7 Power Consumption Measurement

To calculate the instantaneous rate of energy usage or power consumption overhead accurately and consistently, as much as possible, we isolated the pods of each multi-cluster networking solution as described in the previous section. The power consumption overhead added by the multi-cluster networking solution was calculated by measuring the power consumption on the gateway node during the test runs and subtracting that from consumption observed on the gateway node in an idle cluster without the workload. By doing this on both the clusters and adding the overhead observed in each cluster, the total power consumption overhead of each multi-cluster networking solution was obtained. However, for Istio mesh, where it was not completely possible to isolate the components onto a dedicated node due to the presence of sidecar containers, the power consumption overhead on the gateway node was added to the power consumption of each of the sidecar containers of the client and server pods reported by Kepler to arrive at the cumulative overhead. Cluster nodes were configured at the BIOS level with the *Performance per Watt* system profile, maximum memory frequency, Turbo Boost, and C states. The KPI for these tests is power consumption overhead represented in *Watts*.

4 Evaluation

In this section, we first discuss the results of the network performance tests. Next, we examine the Stream tests, followed by the Request-Response tests. We then present the results of the HTTP tests. After that, we analyze resource consumption overhead, followed by a discussion on energy consumption overhead. Finally, we summarize our findings and discuss threats to validity.

4.1 Network Performance Baseline

To quantify the overhead introduced by the networking solutions, we first measured the baseline performance of inter and intra-cluster networks without employing the solutions. This way, we have a performance baseline against which we can compare the three multi-cluster networking solutions. Since the primary function of a multi-cluster networking solution is to enable communication between microservices as though they were on the same cluster, this baseline acts as useful framework for comparisons.

Clusternet and hostnet are two distinct networking solutions within Kubernetes, each with its own characteristics and use cases. Clusternet enables pods leverage the CNI for network connectivity, OVN-Kubernetes in our scenario. On the other hand, hostnet is a networking mode in Kubernetes that allows pods to share the network namespace of the host node. This means that pods can directly access the host network interfaces and IP addresses, usually showcasing better performance with minimal overheads incurred.

First, we measured network throughput as we gradually increased the workload. We increased the message size from 64B to 8192B and scaled the number of threads from 1 to 4. Figure 7

illustrates the resulting throughput, with the x-axis representing the workload (i.e., message size and number of threads) and the y-axis indicating throughput in Gbps. Throughput rises with the increasing message sizes and number of threads, reaching peak values of 22.66 Gbps, 22.56 Gbps, 21.64 Gbps, and 21.66 Gbps for intra-cluster hostnet p2p, inter-cluster hostnet p2p, intra-cluster clusternet p2p, and intra-cluster clusternet p2s (pod-to-service), respectively, demonstrating that both clusternet and hostnet can support nearly identical peak loads.

Figure 7: Baseline network throughput performance. Each point shows the average, with error bars representing the standard deviation. Lines are included purely for visual clarity, as the measurements are discrete and do not imply continuous values.

Next, we examined the number of transactions per second as the workload increased (via number of threads and message size). Figure 8 shows these results, where the x-axis reflects message size and number of threads, and the y-axis shows transactions per second. As message size grows, the transactions per second decline. The maximum observed transactions per second were 240,276, 193,172, 143,746, and 143,304 for intra-cluster hostnet p2p, inter-cluster hostnet p2p, intra-cluster clusternet p2p, and intra-cluster clusternet p2s, respectively.

Figure 8: Baseline Request-Response performance. Each point represents the average, with error bars for the standard deviation. Lines are added purely for visual clarity, as the measurements are discrete and do not imply continuous values.

4.2 Stream Tests

We repeated the STREAM experiments while the three multi-cluster networking solutions were deployed. The results are visualized in Figure 9, with the horizontal axis showing the workload and the vertical axis the throughput in Gbps. It's important to note that Submariner, when using the default IPsec configuration, faces a scalability limitation due to the Linux Kernel's IPsec implementation. This implementation restricts each connection or encryption to a single CPU core. Further investigation revealed that this is a recognized limitation within both the IETF and Linux IPsec communities, which results in Submariner experiencing the lowest throughput. Additionally, it is worth noting that Skupper exhibited a bottleneck at about 8 Gbps and could not go past that despite increasing the message size and number of threads.

Compared to intra-cluster clusternet p2s (red dashed line), all solutions have reduced throughput from a message size of 1024B onward. At peak load, the baseline achieved was 22.66 Gbps, whereas the network solutions reached 8.07 Gbps (Skupper), 2.59 Gbps (Submariner), and 14.87 Gbps (Istio). While Skupper and Submariner exhibit minimal variation, Istio shows significant variation (indicated by the standard deviations depicted as error bars) when more than one thread is used. Overall, throughput decreases depending on the solution's overhead, dropping to about one-third, one-tenth, or 7/10 of the baseline, with Istio achieving the highest throughput and Submariner the lowest.

Figure 9: Throughput comparison, using intra-cluster clusternet p2s as the baseline. Each point represents the average, with error bars indicating the standard deviation. Lines are added solely for visual clarity, as measurements are discrete and do not suggest continuous values.

4.3 Request-Response Tests

To assess the number of transactions per second supported by each multi-cluster networking solutions, we repeated the Request-Request experiments with each deployed solution. Figure 10 illustrates the results, with message size and thread count on the x-axis and transactions per second on the y-axis. All solutions exhibited fewer transactions per second than the intra-cluster clusternet p2s (red dashed line). At peak load, the baseline achieved 87,742 transactions per second, while Skupper reached 13,669, Submariner 15,489, and Istio 23,487. Unlike the baseline, the three solutions showed minimal variability, with error bars barely visible. For message sizes 64B and 1024B, Submariner achieved the highest transactions per second, but for size 8192B, Istio surpassed Submariner. Skupper

consistently yielded the lowest transactions per second across all workloads. In summary, deploying these multi-cluster networking solutions reduces transactions per second to approximately one-sixth (Skupper), 3/10 (Submariner), and one-fourth (Istio) of the baseline performance.

Figure 10: Transactions per second comparison, using intra-cluster clusternet p2s as the baseline. Each point represents the average, with error bars indicating the standard deviation. Lines are added solely for visual clarity, as measurements are discrete and do not suggest continuous values.

4.4 HTTP Tests

Besides the achieved throughput and the transactions per second, we wanted to understand how the multi-cluster networking solutions affect the long-tail latency of Layer 7 applications, which can indicate important end-user focused metrics like page load times. Figure 11 illustrates the latency of the different multi-cluster networking solutions, with percentiles on the horizontal axis and latency in milliseconds on the vertical axis.

Istio displayed the highest latency, reaching up to 14.5 times the latency of Submariner. It also showed the most variation in latency. It is worth noting that Istio ambient mode (sidecarless) is supposed to significantly reduce the observed latency and resource usage overhead [2].

On the other hand, Skupper's latency remained comparable to Submariner's up to the 99th percentile, beyond which it increased, peaking at four times Submariner's latency. Submariner had the lowest latency and variation overall, with an increase of just 4 ms from the 50th to the 100th percentile.

Figure 11: Latency comparison with each point represents the average, with error bars indicating the standard deviation.

4.5 Resource Consumption Overhead

Previously, we focused on network performance; now, we are shifting focus to analyze the incurred overhead with each multi-cluster networking solution. Specifically, we measured the CPU utilization overhead during the Stream experiments, as outlined in Section 3.6. Figure 12 displays the the number of used CPU cores for each multi-cluster networking solution, with the x-axis indicating message size and number of threads and the y-axis representing CPU overhead. Among the solutions, Skupper showed the highest overhead, peaking at 11 cores, while Submariner had the lowest, with a maximum of 4 cores. Istio exhibited the most variation, as indicated by the error bars showing standard deviation. Notably, for each solution, higher thread counts led to greater overhead due to increased concurrent traffic flows. For Skupper and Submariner, the highest CPU overhead was observed with the 64B message size in the 4 threads configuration as smaller message size results in more packets that need to be pushed. Istio does not exhibit this behavior and shows some inconsistencies due to its sidecar-based approach.

Figure 12: CPU overhead comparison with each point represents the average, with error bars indicating the standard deviation. Lines are added solely for visual clarity, as measurements are discrete and do not suggest continuous values.

Every CPU cycle dedicated to running the components of these solutions reduces the CPU time available for applications. As a result, cluster administrators and architects must carefully consider overhead in their evaluations. Therefore, we reevaluate the Stream test by normalizing throughput concerning the incurred overhead for a fair comparison. Figure 13 presents this normalized view, where the x-axis shows message size and number of threads, and the y-axis shows normalized throughput in Gbps. Although Istio maintained the highest throughput, Submariner achieved consistently higher output than Skupper throughout the experiment, reversing the observation in Figure 9.

4.6 Power Consumption Overhead

In addition to CPU overhead, we measured power consumption overhead as outlined in Section 3.7. Unlike the other experiments, this analysis focuses exclusively on Stream tests using 4 threads. Figure 14 presents the power consumption overhead, with the x-axis representing message size and number of threads and the y-axis showing power consumption overhead in Watts. Skupper showed the highest rate of instantaneous energy usage, peaking at 195 Watts, followed by Submariner at 156 Watts, which also showed

Figure 13: Normalized throughput comparison with each point represents the average, with error bars indicating the standard deviation. Lines are added solely for visual clarity, as measurements are discrete and do not suggest continuous values.

the highest variation, as indicated by the error bars representing the standard deviation. In contrast, Istio required about 6/10 of Skupper’s power consumption (with a peak value of 121 Watts). Notably, the rankings for Submariner and Istio are reversed compared to their CPU overhead performance. Similar to the CPU resource usage overhead, the power consumption overhead is the highest for the 64B message size.

Figure 14: Power consumption overhead comparison with each point represents the average, with error bars indicating the standard deviation. Lines are added solely for visual clarity, as measurements are discrete and do not suggest continuous values.

4.7 Discussion of Evaluation Findings

We conducted five different sets of experiments to investigate the performance of multi-cluster networking solutions. We summarize the main findings of our evaluation as follows:

Skupper reached moderate throughput (8.07 Gbps) due to a bottleneck and exhibited the highest CPU usage and power consumption overhead, peaking at 11 CPU cores and 195 W peak power respectively. Latency remained close to Submariner’s up to the 99th percentile, but it increased sharply beyond this point, reaching up to four times that of Submariner.

Submariner due to its default IPsec configuration encountered scalability limitations, resulting in the lowest throughput (2.59

Gbps). However, it had the lowest overall latency, with only a 4 ms increase from the 50th to the 100th percentile, and the lowest resource consumption, including 4 CPU cores and 156 Watts peak power consumption overhead.

Istio achieved the highest throughput (14.87 Gbps), but exhibited the highest variability in latency and resource usage. Its latency peaked at up to 14.5 times that of Submariner, especially beyond the 99th percentile. It exhibited the lowest peak power consumption overhead (122 Watts) and displayed substantial latency variation under multithreaded conditions.

In summary, our evaluation of Skupper, Submariner, and Istio reveals unique trade-offs in performance and resource efficiency. Figure 15 illustrates these trade-offs, with each measured performance aspect normalized between 0 to 1, where 1 represents the optimal value (e.g., minimal overhead or maximum throughput). The value for each performance aspect before normalization is equal to the average over the respective experiment. For example, Submariner is ideal for applications that prioritize low latency, high number of transactions, and resource efficiency, especially when consistent performance is crucial. In contrast, Istio is suitable for workloads that require high throughput, a large number of transactions, and moderate resource consumption, particularly when energy efficiency is a concern. However, its varying latency under multi-threaded conditions should be carefully evaluated for applications with stringent latency requirements. Skupper has the least prerequisites and presents the least complexity to set up and operate. Ultimately, the choice of solution depends on the application's specific requirements, including throughput, latency, resource consumption, and operational complexity.

Figure 15: Overview of the performance comparison. Each performance aspect is normalized between 0 and 1, with 1 being the best value (e.g., low overhead or high throughput).

4.8 Threats to Validity

While we conducted various experiments to assess the network performance of multi-cluster networking solutions, a key limitation is that these were performed exclusively within an enterprise data center environment. As a result, the outcomes may vary in other environments, such as cloud domains. However, we selected this environment to maintain control over variables and minimize

experimental variability. Additionally, each experiment involved using a single application; since our primary focus was on networking performance, we do not anticipate significant differences with alternative applications. Our experiments were also limited to a two-cluster setup, leaving the scalability of these solutions with a higher number of clusters as an area for future research.

5 Conclusion

Managing multi-cluster Kubernetes environments introduces significant complexity, particularly in enabling seamless communication across distributed clusters. This industry paper comprehensively analyzes network performance characteristics for three popular open-source multi-cluster networking solutions: Skupper, Submariner, and Istio. Our evaluation shows that each solution presents distinct performance and resource efficiency trade-offs. Submariner proves advantageous for low-latency applications where consistent performance is critical, while Istio supports high-throughput workloads with moderate resource use, although latency may fluctuate. Selecting the appropriate solution requires aligning application needs—such as throughput, latency, resource consumption, and energy efficiency—with the capabilities of each system. We hope that our analysis provides valuable insights for organizations seeking to optimize the network performance of their multi-cluster Kubernetes deployments.

6 Future Work

This paper's scope was confined to evaluating the multi-cluster networking data plane by comparing the performance of three multi-cluster networking solutions using micro-benchmarks, focusing on KPIs such as throughput and latency. In future work, we plan to examine the performance of the data plane through real-world benchmarks involving messaging, databases, and applications based on microservices architecture. Other important areas to explore are key capabilities of the control plane, such as service discovery time (the speed at which services created in one cluster are detected by another) and service failover time. Our goal is to provide a more comprehensive analysis of the control plane's role in the comparative performance of these solutions. Lastly, we focused on the interconnection of two clusters, but we intend to investigate scenarios involving multiple interconnected clusters. This approach will add a new dimension to our testing and help us assess the impact on various performance and scalability metrics, enhancing our understanding of how these systems function in more complex environments.

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